

Kinetics of Ruthenium(III)-catalysed Oxidation of Methyl Glycol by Acidic Solutions of *N*-Bromosuccinimide

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Kinetic data obtained in Ru^{III}-catalysed oxidation of methyl glycol by acidic solutions of *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) in presence of mercuric acetate show first order kinetics in each NBS, methyl glycol, H⁺ and Ru^{III}. Zero effect of mercuric acetate, ionic strength, and negative effect of Cl⁻ ions and succinimide addition were observed. Negative dielectric effect and significant solvent isotope effect ($k_1, D_2O/H_2O = 1.71 - 2.24$) were observed at 35°. Various thermodynamic parameters have been computed. A suitable mechanism in agreement with kinetic observations has been proposed.

EARLIER, NBS has been used in estimation of several organic compounds^{1,2}. Recently, kinetic investigations on NBS oxidation of alcohols^{3,4}, ketones⁵⁻⁷ and esters⁸ have been reported, but so far, no attempt has been made to probe the catalytic role of Ru^{III} in NBS oxidations. The present paper reports the kinetic data obtained in Ru^{III}-catalysed oxidation of methyl glycol by NBS in perchloric acid media in the presence of mercuric acetate, and mechanistic routes in the light of Ru^{III} catalysis have been discussed.

Experimental

Perchloric acid (60%) (E. Merck), sodium perchlorate, mercuric acetate and succinimide (H & W) were used. NBS (S. Merck, G.R.) solution was always prepared fresh and its strength checked iodometrically. The solution of methyl glycol (B.D.H., L.R.) was prepared by weighing the sample. Ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson Matthey) solution was prepared by dissolving the sample in HCl of known strength. D₂O (99.4%) was obtained from B.A.R.C. (Bombay).

The reaction was initiated by adding requisite amount of methyl glycol to the reaction bottle containing all other reagents and maintained at the desired temperature ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). The progress of the reaction was followed by estimating unconsumed [NBS] iodometrically using starch as indicator. The kinetic results were reproducible within $\pm 2.8\%$.

Results and Discussion

Ru^{III}-catalysed oxidation of methyl glycol by acidified NBS was studied over a wide range of concentrations of the reactants. Table 1 represents first order constants for varying [NBS], [Hg(OAc)₂], temperature and ionic strength (μ). First order in NBS is further supported through the linear

plots of log unconsumed [NBS] vs time for varying [NBS] where a set of parallel lines were obtained. First order dependence on each methyl glycol, H⁺ and Ru^{III} was obvious from log k_1 vs log [methyl glycol] or log [H⁺] or log [Ru^{III}] plots (Fig. 1) yielding straight lines with slopes nearly one.

Fig. 1. $\log k_1$ vs $\log$ [Methyl glycol] or $\log$ [H⁺] or $\log$ [Ru^{III}] plots at 35°, [NBS] = 1.09×10^{-3} M, [KCl] = 4.0×10^{-2} M, [Hg(OAc)₂] = 4.00×10^{-3} M at (A) [HClO₄] = 1.00×10^{-2} M and [Ru^{III}] = 2.20×10^{-7} M (B) [Methyl glycol] = 5.00×10^{-3} M and [Ru^{III}] = 2.20×10^{-7} M, and (C) [Methyl glycol] = 5.00×10^{-3} M and [HClO₄] = 1.00×10^{-2} M.

Table 2 reports the decreasing effect of added Cl⁻ ions and succinimide and positive effect of successive additions of acetic acid and D₂O. The data at 30, 35, 40 and 45° led to compute the energy of activation ($\Delta E^\ddagger$) 14.20 ± 0.20 kcal mol⁻¹, frequency factor (A) $7.84 \pm 0.25 \times 10^9$ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, entropy of activation ($\Delta S^\ddagger$) -14.18 ± 0.16 e.u., heat activation ($\Delta H^\ddagger$) 13.58 ± 0.20 kcal mol⁻¹ and free energy of activation ($\Delta F^\ddagger$) 17.95 ± 0.25 kcal mol⁻¹. Estimation of unconsumed [NBS] in various sets of experiments performed with varying [NBS]—

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF [NBS], [Hg(OAc)₂], TEMPERATURE AND IONIC STRENGTH (μ) ON REACTION RATE

[Methyl glycol] = 5.00 × 10⁻³ M, [HClO₄] = 1.00 × 10⁻² M, [Ru^{III}] = 2.20 × 10⁻⁷ M, [KCl] = 4.00 × 10⁻³ M, Temp = 35° (unless otherwise stated)

[NBA] × 10 ⁴ M	μ* × 10 ³ M	[Hg(OAc) ₂] × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
5.0	5.1	4.0	18.8
6.4	5.1	4.0	18.7
10.9	5.1	4.0	18.7
12.8	5.1	4.0	18.9
16.8	5.1	4.0	18.9
26.0	5.1	4.0	18.8
35.0	5.1	4.0	18.7
10.9	8.0	6.0	18.8
10.9	8.0	8.0	18.8
10.9	8.0	14.0	17.7
10.9	8.0	18.0	18.7
10.9	8.0	24.0	18.7
10.9	10.0	4.0	18.8
10.9	25.0	4.0	18.7
10.9	35.0	4.0	18.6
10.9	45.0	4.0	18.6
10.9	50.0	4.0	18.7
10.9	5.1	4.0	10.6 ^a
10.9	5.1	4.0	27.0 ^b
10.9	5.1	4.0	61.1 ^c

* Change in ionic strength (μ) was affected by addition of suitable amounts of sodium perchlorate. ^a 30°. ^b 40°. ^c 45°.

[methyl glycol] ratios showed that one mole of NBS was consumed for the oxidation of one mole of methyl glycol. The end-product corresponding to methyl glycoldehyde was tested by tlc and also through dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNP) derivative⁹.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ADDITIONS OF ACETIC ACID, D₂O, Cl⁻ IONS AND SUCCINIMIDE ON REACTION RATE

[NBS] = 1.09 × 10⁻³ M, [Methyl glycol] = 5.00 × 10⁻³ M, [Hg(OAc)₂] = 4.00 × 10⁻³ M, [HClO₄] = 1.00 × 10⁻² M, [Ru^{III}] = 2.20 × 10⁻⁷ M, [KCl] = 4.00 × 10⁻³ M (unless otherwise stated), Temp = 35°

Acetic acid Vol %	D ₂ O Vol %	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	[Cl ⁻] × 10 ³ M	[M]* × 10 ³ M	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
0	0	18.7	2.0	—	22.0
20	0	34.7	4.0	—	18.7
35	0	34.7	10.0	—	12.5
50	0	39.4	20.0	—	10.4
60	0	54.2	30.0	—	9.7
0	30	32.0	4.0	0.4	10.4
0	50	38.2	4.0	2.0	2.5
—	—	—	4.0	3.0	2.1

* [Succinimide].

Insignificant effect of mercuric acetate indicates that it acts as a scavenger¹⁰ for Br⁻ ions formed in the reaction and exists as unionised HgBr₂ or HgBr₂²⁻ and thus avoids any possible bromine oxidation, which may be produced as

Mercuric acetate thus ensures the oxidation purely through NBS and in no way it is involved in NBS oxidation.

Ruthenium(III) chloride has been reported to exist as [RuCl₆]³⁻ in hydrochloric acid solution, which is in equilibrium^{11,12} with [RuCl₅.H₂O]²⁻,

The negative effect of Cl⁻ ions addition suggests that Cl⁻ ions are formed in a pre-equilibrium prior to the rate-controlling step and thus confirms that equilibrium (2) exists to the right side. This further suggests that [RuCl₅.H₂O]²⁻ is the real reactive species of ruthenium(III) chloride in the present investigation.

Equilibria (3–5) are reported to exist in acidified NBS solutions,

It is obvious from the above equilibria that either NBS itself or protonated NBS, viz N⁺BSH or H₂O Br⁺, is the possible oxidising species of NBS. If NBS is taken as the possible oxidising species, the rate law derived on this basis fails to explain significant D₂O effect, hydrogen ion dependence and negative effect of succinimide, and thus NBS as real oxidising species is ruled out. If protonated NBS, i.e. N⁺BSH is taken to be the possible oxidising species, zero effect of succinimide should be observed. Contrary to this, negative effect of succinimide does not allow us to assume N⁺BSH as real oxidising species of NBS. The only choice left with us is to assume H₂O Br⁺ as the real oxidising species.

The following reaction steps are suggested on the basis of the above discussion. Here, M is succinimide and S is methyl glycol.

where, S = CH₂OCH₂CH₂OH, S⁺ = CH₂OCH₂C⁺HOH and S' = CH₂OCH₂CHO. The rate of the

reaction in terms of consumption of NBS is given by equation (6),

$$\frac{-d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = k_2[\text{S}][\text{C}_2] \quad (6)$$

The total $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}$ may be written as

$$[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{C}_1] + [\text{C}_2] + [\text{C}_3] \quad (7)$$

Considering steps (i-v) and equation (7) we have equation (8) with reasonable assumption, $K_1 K_3 + k'_{-1} K_1 [\text{M}] \gg k'_{-1} [\text{M}][\text{Cl}^-]$, where $K'_3 = K_3 [\text{H}_2\text{O}]$,

$$\frac{-d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = \frac{k'_1 k_2 K_4 [\text{NBS}][\text{H}^+][\text{S}][\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}]_{\text{T}}}{1 + (K'_1)^{-1}[\text{Cl}^-] + k'_{-1}(K'_3)^{-1}[\text{M}]} \quad (8)$$

The rate law (equation 8) is in complete agreement with all experimental results. The magnitude of the solvent isotope effect also supports the proposed mechanism. The higher rate value in D_2O indicates a pre-equilibrium fast proton transfer with specified catalysed reaction¹⁸ (step II). Positive intercepts on 1/rate axis are obtained in plots of 1/rate vs $[\text{Cl}^-]$ and 1/rate vs $[\text{M}]$. This clearly explains the negative effect of Cl^- ions and succinimide on rate and thus supports the proposed mechanism.

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